

STUDING MEDICINAL PLANTS (PHYTONYMS) IN THE SECTION OF PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article will discuss the methods of easy study and teaching students of higher medical educational institutions the names of medicinal plants (phytonyms) in the discipline of Latin and medical terminology in the section of pharmaceutical terminology

Indeed, there is a special charm in our land of the highest mountains, green valleys, forests, rivers and lakes, and even deserts. Especially due to its location in a region where several biogeographic regions intersect, the plant world is characterized by its extremely colorful nature. Generous nature proportionates the whole being in life. All living creatures in it live, flourish, multiply and, if necessary, take ointments from each other, enjoy the sources of vital needs. From this it can be understood that every creature in nature, every plant has its own healing property.

There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. These are used in scientific and folk medicine from about 120 plant species growing and cultured in natural conditions. Currently, about 40-47% of medicines used in medicine are obtained from plant raw materials. The study of medicinal plant names (phytonyms) in Latin according to the pharmaceutical nomenclature requires its healing properties. Another important aspect is that plant names are necessarily written in initials in Latin. Under the term phytonym (Greek phyton-plant + onym-name), the names of plants are understood.

Phytonyms are distinguished from other layers in the vocabulary by their direct connection with the history of socio-political, cultural development of the people, their interaction with customs and traditions. In the course of Latin and medical terminology, the study of botanical names is the assimilation of new linguistic materials with many lexical units, which can be ambiguous concepts, and students, as a rule, may not have an associative understanding of this topic. Phytonyms are a part of the language that has a long history. In addition to folk life, culture, history, socio-political views, they preserve the ancient traditions inherent in the language and language of the people who created them.

Plants can also be called differently in different oases of the same country, and the etymology of botanical names is always interesting and multifaceted. The task of Latin teachers is to create motivational conditions for students to consciously learn the names of plants in Latin. In the study of botanical terms, it is necessary to start with the introduction of words in Latin, since

when the Latin term fully or partially corresponds to the corresponding word of the Uzbek language, students easily understand and remember the Uzbek equivalent.

For example, "Aloe" is translated as "Aloe" in Latin, "aloy" in Russian, and "aloes" in English, another example of this is "medicinal valerian", "medicinal speedwell", "medicinal calendula (marigold)", "medicinal borago", "kalankhoe", "mountain arnica" and other plants. It is easy to remember the names of this medicinal plant, since in many languages it is written in the same way.

When a student knows the basic 6 different color names in medical terms, he will quickly and easily remember the name of the plants associated with that color name from Latin to Uzbek. For example, depending on the color of some plant flowers: Bryonia **alba**- white bronnia, Lamium **album**-white lamium, Viscum **album**-white mistletoe, Salix **alba**-white willow, Melilotus **albus**- melilot white (Latin **albus**-white), Centaurea **cyaneus**- blue beetle (Greek **cyano**-blue), Crataegus **sanguineus**- red Hawthorn (**sanguineus**- blood color), Ribes **nigrum**- black currant, Populus **nigra**-black birch tree, (Latin **niger**-black) Aronia **melanocarpa**-black-fruited aronia (Greek **melano**-black, **carpus**-fruit), Polemonium **coeruleum**-blueberry (Latin **coeruleus**-blue), Nuphar **lutea**-yellow nufar (Latin **luteus**-yellow), Viola **tricolor**-tricolor violet (Latin **tri**-three, **color**-colour), Eucalyptus **cinerea**- grey eucalyptus (Latin **cinereus**-grey), Rhodiola **rosea**- Rhodiola pink, (Latin **roseus**-pink); the names of plants by their place of passage: Equisetum **arvense**- Equisetum field, Fragaria **vesca**- Wild strawberries, Oxycoccus **palustris**- Marsh cranberries, the names of countries: Atractylodes **chinensis**- atractylodes **Chinese**, Atractylodes **japonica**- Atractylodes **Japanese**, Berberis **amurensis**- **Amur** barberry, Berberis **pacifica**- Berberis **Pacific**, Dioscorea **caucasica**- Dioscorea of the **Caucasus**, Pinus **koreansis**- **Korean** pine, Patrinia **sibirica**- Patrinia **Siberian**; looking at the shape of the plants, for example: Achillea **millefolium**- Yarrow, (Latin **mille**-thousand, **folium**-leaf), Berberis **crassifolia**- Berberis thick – leaved, (Latin **crassus**-thick, **folium**-leaf), Betula **platyphilla**- flat-leaved birch, (Greek **platy**-plain, **phillo**-leaf), Chelidonium **majus**- Celandine large, (Latin **major**, **majus**-large), Leonurus **cardiaca**- Motherwort, (Latin **cardiacus**-cordial), Eucalyptus **globulus**- eucalyptus globules- (Latin **globulus**-spherical), Tilia **cordata**-Linden (lime-tree) heart-shaped (Latin **cor**, **cordis**-heart); plant names depending on the ingredients: Mentha **piperita**- Peppermint, (Latin **piper**-pepper); Artemisia **absinthium**-Wormwood bitter (Latin **absinthius**-bitter); depending on the seasons, for example: Rosa **majalis** (Latin **majalis**-may date), Primula **veris**- Primula (Latin **primus**-first, **ver**-spring) and others can be exemplified. Through these analogies, the student can easily remember phytonyms.

Good mastery of pharmaceutical terms is aimed at training professionals with universal knowledge, who can understand medical terms in their field well, which will help them think independently, critically and creatively, develop beliefs and motivate them to confidently enter into social relationships, regardless of the profession chosen by them.

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